

TIME-TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE ON FLEXURAL STRENGTH
OF PITCH-BASED CARBON FIBER UNIDIRECTIONAL CFRP LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The three-point flexural fracture behavior of unidirectional CFRP laminates made with the recently developed high-performance pitch-based carbon fiber XN40 was evaluated over a wide range of temperatures and times. The same experiments were conducted on the PAN-based carbon fiber M40 and the pitch-based carbon fiber P55S, and a comparison of the results for these three CFRP laminates clarified the characteristics of X-CFRP. Those results are as follows:

(1)The flexural strength of the three types of CFRP vary greatly depending on the temperature and the strain rate. The master curve for the flexural strength of the three CFRPs are subject to a reciprocation law between time and temperature, and the time-and-temperature shift factors for the flexural strength of the various CFRPs are in close agreement.

(2)The reciprocation times can be divided into three regions depending on the type of fracture of X-CFRP. The start of the fracture depends on the microbuckling of the fiber in the long reduced time region, on the compressive fracture of the fiber in the intermediate reduced time region, and on the tensile fracture of the fiber in the short reduced time region.

(3)In the intermediate reduced time region, the flexural strength of X-CFRP exhibits unique behavior different from the other two CFRPs. In the region, the flexural strength of X-CFRP increases sharply as the time becomes shorter.

KEYWORDS: Flexural; Fracture; Strain rate; Fiber, graphite; Viscoelastic

1. INTRODUCTION

Pitch-based carbon fiber is classified into two types: general-purpose grade and high-performance (or high modulus of elasticity) grade. Recently high-performance pitch-based carbon fiber has been developed. However, the mechanical properties of CFRP made from

this new fiber have not been fully understood.

The mechanical properties of the resin used as the matrix of CFRP vary greatly depending on the time and temperature, the resin exhibits viscoelastic behavior. Therefore it can be expected that the mechanical properties and fracturing of CFRP will also largely depend on the time and temperature. Detailed evaluations have already been conducted on the time-temperature dependence of the mechanical behavior of CFRP made with PAN-based carbon fiber, and the results have shown that the time and temperature have a strong effect not only on the CFRP's mechanical behavior but also on its fracture mechanism. Therefore it is thought that the characteristics of the fracture behavior of the carbon fiber could be clarified by examining the fracture mechanisms of the CFRP across a wide range of times and temperatures.

In this study, three-point bending tests were conducted across a wide range of times and temperatures on unidirectional CFRP laminates made from recently developed high-performance pitch-based carbon fiber and, for comparison, both PAN-based carbon fiber and conventional pitch-based carbon fiber. The purpose was to understand the characteristics of CFRP made from pitch-based carbon fiber by learning the time and temperature dependence of the fracture behavior exhibited by these tests.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Test Materials The three types of carbon fiber used were the recently developed pitch-based carbon fiber XN40 (Nippon Oil, brand name Granoc), the PAN-based carbon fiber M40 (Toray Industries, brand name Torayca) and the conventional pitch-based carbon fiber P55S (Amoco Performance Products, brand name Thornel). M40 and P55S have stiffness comparable to that of XN40. The specifications and mechanical properties of these fibers are shown in Table 1. Prepreg sheets made from these fibers (the matrix was the epoxy resin formulation 25C manufactured by Nippon Oil Company) were stacked into layers and formed into 3mm thick unidirectional CFRP laminates. The fiber volume fraction was 53 to 58%. In the following, these three types of unidirectional laminates are referred to as X-CFRP(XN40), M-CFRP(M40), and P-CFRP(P55S).

Figure 1 shows the temperature characteristics of the storage modulus E' and the loss modulus E'' at the frequency of 1 Hz for the epoxy resin 25C used as the matrix of the CFRP laminates. The glass transition temperature of the matrix resin is 141°C, and, as shown in the Figure 1, the mechanical properties vary greatly within the measured temperature range.

2.2 Experimental Method Each test specimen was a strip 3mm thick, 10mm wide, and 80mm long having a constant cross section. A tension tester with a constant temperature oven was used to conduct the three-point bending tests. The span length was 60mm. The tests were conducted at 12 to 14 fixed temperatures in the range of -60 to 180°C at the testing machine crosshead speeds of 0.02, 2.0, and 200 mm/min. The flexural strength was then obtained from the stress-strain curve, and the fracture surface of the test specimens were observed with an SEM.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Stress–Strain Curves Figure 2 shows typical stress–strain curves obtained from the flexural tests for X-CFRP, M-CFRP, and P-CFRP at the strain rate of 2 mm/min. This figure shows the curves for three temperatures: -60°C , the lowest temperature tested; 160°C , the highest temperature tested; and 140°C , which is close to the glass transition temperature of the matrix resin. The stress–strain curves for all three laminates exhibit no temperature-dependent changes in the temperature range substantially below 141°C , which is the glass transition temperature of the matrix resin; for each specimen, the stress increases relative to the strain, followed by a sharp drop in the curve at the point of maximum stress. However, when the test temperature is in a higher range near or above the glass transition temperature, a strong temperature dependence appears, and the slope of the curve decreases as the temperature increases. The major difference between the stress–strain curves for the pitch-based and PAN-based laminates is that in the low-temperature region the curve for the PAN-based laminate is nearly linear up to the point of fracture, while the pitch-based P-CFRP shows slightly non-linear behavior beginning in the low-strain region and the slope of its curve is smaller relative to the increase in stress. This non-linear behavior appears more clearly with X-CFRP, which has a large fracture strain, and, X-CFRP has the largest fracture elongation of any of the three laminates.

3.2 Fracture Surface Figure 3 shows the fracture surface of X-CFRP after a flexural test at a strain rate of 2 mm/min. When the fracture is observed during the test to proceed from the tension side of the loading point on the test specimen, a tensile fracture region appears in which fiber pullouts are observed across the entire fracture surface, as in the -60°C case of Figure 3. On the other hand, when the fracture has first spread to a certain depth from the compression side of the loading point, followed by an instantaneous final fracture (as in the room temperature and 130°C cases of Figure 3), the fracture surface of the test specimen can clearly be divided into two regions separated by a boundary at a certain depth in the surface. The first region is the compressive fracture region, which is the upper part of the surface; no fiber pullouts are observed there. The second is the tensile fracture region, which is the lower part of the fracture surface; in this region, fiber pullouts are observed. At the higher temperature of 160°C , microbuckling has clearly occurred at the compression side of the loading point in the test specimen, after which a fiber tensile fracture occurs on the tension side as well; however, the test specimen has not broken apart. Although Figure 3 shows only the fracture surface for X-CFRP at the strain rate of 2 mm/min, the same three types of fracture can be observed with other strain rates and with M-CFRP and P-CFRP.

Figure 4 shows the fractographs of individual fibers in the compressive fracture region of various CFRP laminates. Even though the fracture begins on the compression side of the test specimen, detailed observation of the fractographs of the fibers in the compressive fracture region reveals that there are two major types of fracture surface depending on the type of fiber, the test temperature, and the strain rate. The first type of surface is flat and perpendicular to the orientation of the fibers; this type of fracture is observed at high temperature with

all three types of CFRP laminates. In the other type, which is observed at low temperatures, the fiber fracture surfaces are very rough and uneven. In the first type, observation of the test specimens shows that the fracture begins with microbuckling resulting from mutual interference between the fibers and the surrounding matrix. In the second type, observation of the fracture surfaces suggests that the fracture begins with the compressive fracture of the fibers themselves.

3.3 Master Curve of Flexural Strength The graphs on the left side of Figure 5 show the flexural strength of the three CFRP laminates at a fixed temperature relative to the inverse of the strain rate (i.e., relative to time). By moving these points horizontally along the logarithmic-time axis, we can form the nearly smooth curve shown on the right and so obtain the master curve of the flexural strength at the reference temperature of 150°C. This indicates the existence of a reciprocation law between time and temperature for the flexural strength of CFRP laminates. Figure 6 shows the time-temperature shift factor $a_{T_0}(T)$, that is, the amount of horizontal shift. The values $a_{T_0}(T)$ for each CFRP laminates can be approximated at low and high temperatures using Arrhenius' equation with two different activation energies ΔH . The value of ΔH for the fracture of CFRP laminates in the high-temperature region is very close to the value of $\Delta H=725$ kJ/mol for the mechanical behavior of the resin in the same high-temperature region; this indicates that the mechanical behavior of the resin strongly influences the time and temperature dependence of CFRP fracturing. However, the value of ΔH for the fracture of CFRP laminates in the low-temperature region is far different from the resin's value of $\Delta H=200$ kJ/mol, so it is difficult to say that the mechanical behavior of the matrix resin contributes to the time and temperature dependence of CFRP laminate fracturing in this temperature region. This suggests that, in the low-temperature region, the fracture begins with the carbon fiber itself, regardless of the tension or compression.

Figure 7 shows the test points on the master curve for X-CFRP's flexural strength in Figure 5 in term of the type of fracture. This indicates that the types of fracture can be clearly divided into three categories on the master curve: tensile fracture of the fiber, compressive fracture of the fiber, and microbuckling fracture of the fiber. In each of these regions, a distinctive flexural strength-time curve is exhibited. The same observation can be made about M-CFRP and P-CFRP as well.

Figure 8 summarizes the flexural strength master curves for the three CFRP laminates and indicates their separate fracture regions. In the long reduced time region (i.e., in the high-temperature region), the fracture of all three types begins with microbuckling, the flexural strength-time curves are almost identical, and the flexural strength decreases relative to time. In the short reduced time region, each CFRP laminate exhibits a unique type of flexural fracture behavior. The flexural strength of X-CFRP increases slightly relative to time in the short reduced time region, and the fracture begins with the tensile fracture of the fiber on the tension side of the test specimen. In the intermediate region, the flexural strength drops sharply relative to the increase in time, exhibiting an extremely close time dependence; the fracture in this region begins with the compressive fracture of the fibers on the compression

side of the test specimen. In the short reduced time region, M-CFRP exhibits almost the same steady level of flexural strength relative to the time increase as shown by X-CFRP; after entering the intermediate time region, M-CFRP exhibits a slow decrease in flexural strength relative to the increase in time. In both the short and intermediate time regions, the fibers of M-CFRP undergo compressive fracture, the same as for X-CFRP in the intermediate time region. The flexural strength of P-CFRP exhibits a slow increase relative to time from the short to the intermediate time regions; the fibers undergo tensile fracture, the same as for X-CFRP in the short time region. In the intermediate and long time regions, however, the flexural strength of P-CFRP decreases relative to the increase in time, and compressive fracture of the fibers occurs in only a small region.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In order to clarify the characteristics of CFRP using high-performance pitch-based carbon fiber, tests were conducted across a wide range of temperatures and strain rates to evaluate the flexural fracture behavior of three types of CFRP: the unidirectional CFRP laminate X-CFRP, which used the recently developed XN40 fiber, and, for comparison, M-CFRP, which used the PAN-based carbon fiber M40, and P-CFRP, which used the conventional pitch-based carbon fiber P55S. The fracture types of X-CFRP can be divided into three regions depending on the temperature and the strain rate (i.e., the time); the flexural strength exhibit distinct changes in accordance with these three regions. In particular, the flexural strength of X-CFRP exhibited a strong time-temperature dependence in the intermediate temperature and time regions; the flexural strength increased sharply at lower temperatures and shorter times, and a temperature and time region was found in which the flexural strength of X-CFRP exceeds the flexural strength of the other two types of CFRP.

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REFERENCES

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TABLE1. Specifications and mechanical properties of fibers

		XN40	M40	P55S
Diameter of mono filament	μm	10.0	6.5	10.0
Specific gravity		2.10	1.81	2.1
Elastic modulus	GPa	402	392	380
Tensile strength	GPa	3.43	2.8	2.1
Ultimate strain	%	0.85	0.6	0.5

FIGURE 1. Temperature dependence of storage modulus E' and loss modulus E'' of matrix resin (Frequency: 1Hz)

FIGURE 2. Load-deflection curve of various CFRP ($V=2\text{mm/min}$)

FIGURE 3. Observation of fracture surface of X-CFRP ($V=2\text{mm/min}$)

FIGURE 4. Fractographs of fibers at compressive fracture region of various CFRPs. ($V=2\text{mm/min}$)

FIGURE 5. Master curves of flexural strength of various CFRP ($T_0=150^\circ\text{C}$)

○ $T=-60^\circ\text{C}$	● $T=120^\circ\text{C}$
△ $T=-30^\circ\text{C}$	▲ $T=130^\circ\text{C}$
□ $T= 0^\circ\text{C}$	■ $T=140^\circ\text{C}$
▽ $T= \text{R.T.}$	▼ $T=150^\circ\text{C}$
● $T= 60^\circ\text{C}$	● $T=155^\circ\text{C}$
▲ $T= 80^\circ\text{C}$	▲ $T=160^\circ\text{C}$
■ $T=100^\circ\text{C}$	■ $T=170^\circ\text{C}$
▼ $T=110^\circ\text{C}$	▼ $T=180^\circ\text{C}$

FIGURE 6. Time-temperature shift factor $a_{T_0}(T)$ of various CFRP ($T_0=150^\circ\text{C}$)

FIGURE 7. Master curve of flexural strength of X-CFRP ($T_0=150^\circ\text{C}$)

FIGURE 8. Master curves of flexural strength of various CFRP ($T_0=150^\circ\text{C}$)

